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Filippo Angelitti on the Principle of Arithmetical Mean

2020

*“Attamen haud minimum meruere decus astronomi,
qui vario modo hoc principium demonstrare conati
sunt et reducere ad principia magis generalia.”*

Filippo Angelitti

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Introduction

*What follows is the translation into English of three papers published in Latin between 1910 and 1914 by the Italian astronomer Filippo Angelitti (Aielli, 1856 – Palermo, 1931) in issues N° 4424, 4737, and 4768 of the journal *Astronomische Nachrichten*. After reminding us of the axiomatic introduction of the principle of the arithmetical mean enunciated by Gauss in 1809, the Author reviews three famous attempts at deriving that same principle from some more general axiom. He then provides his own proof. I have added some notes to enhance the clarity of mathematical reasoning. A couple of notes are on the translation.*

Rome, September 1st, 2020

Paolo Maccallini

The Principle of Arithmetical Mean

1. In his book entitled *Theoria motus corporum coelestium*, Vol. 2, Sec. III, No 177, Gauss assumed the principle of the arithmetical mean as evident, without proving it, by using these words: “the following hypothesis is generally accepted as an axiom: if a quantity is determined by several direct measures taken with the same method and equally diligently, the arithmetical mean among all the observed values provides the most probable value¹ although not absolutely rigorously, yet very nearly, so that it is always the safest method to adhere to it”.

Analogously, we assume that the sum of the differences between the most probable value and each measure is zero; or that the sum of the squares of the differences between the most probable value and each measure is the smallest possible; these two statements are equivalent to the principle of the arithmetical mean².

Nonetheless, those astronomers who have variously tried to prove this principle and to reduce it to some more general property, earned for themselves a not negligible prestige.

It seems to me extremely useful to recall some of these proofs and to discuss them in depth.

2. First, let me remind you of the remarkably simple proof that Encke published in the issue of the year 1834 of *Berliner Astronomisches Jahrbuch*, p. 262.

Let’s assume that we have only the two measures x_1, x_2 for the same quantity and that they are both reliable or, which is the same, that they have both the same weight, then the most probable value obtained from them obviously is $(x_1 + x_2)/2$: in fact, there is no reason why this value should be closer to one of the two measures than it is to the other one.

If we now have three measures, with the same weight, let us say x_1, x_2, x_3 , we can indicate the most probable value with the notation:

$$f\left(\frac{x_1 + x_2}{2}, x_3\right)$$

or also, by introducing the substitution $s_3 = x_1 + x_2 + x_3$, with the notation

$$f\left(\frac{s_3 - x_3}{2}, x_3\right)$$

and this function assumes the simpler expression $\varphi(s_3)$, since the most probable value must be a symmetric function with respect to all the measures³. The operation indicated by φ must hold for any possible set of values of the three measures: hence, considering the particular case in

¹ The true meaning of this statement by Gauss has been the subject of many speculations since its publication in 1809, and the reader can find a collection of observations made about it by scientists of the 19th century in the book *The Space of Mathematics*, by Javier Echeveria et al. from page 267. I find particularly enlightening the following passage from that book: “Gauss’s view was only that the arithmetic mean is practically the best mode of combining simple observations and that experience has justified its adoption by the accuracy of the results obtained. Gauss was very far from asserting, as a result deduced from the theory of probability, that the arithmetic mean is the most probable value of the quantity observed”.

² This is the main property of the arithmetical mean of the measures x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n : it is the value μ in which the function $f(\mu) = \sum_{k=1}^n (\mu - x_k)^2$ reaches its smallest value, as it is easy verifiable. And this property still holds when we consider the weighted arithmetical mean of the same measures with the weights p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n , respectively: it is the value μ in which the function $f(\mu) = \sum_{k=1}^n p_k (\mu - x_k)^2$ reaches its smallest value.

³ We say that f is a symmetric function of x_1, x_2, x_3 if $f\left(\frac{s_3 - x_1}{2}, x_1\right) = f\left(\frac{s_3 - x_2}{2}, x_2\right) = f\left(\frac{s_3 - x_3}{2}, x_3\right)$. More generally, a function of n variables is symmetric if its value is the same, no matter the order of the arguments.

which $x_1 = x_2 = x_3 = x$, the most probable value is clearly x and we also have $s_3 = 3x$. So, we find

$$\varphi(3x) = x$$

which means that φ is the division by three; hence, in general, the most probable value is given by $s_3/3 = (x_1 + x_2 + x_3)/3$.

Employing the well-known inductive method, it is then possible to show that $(x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n)/n$ is the most probable value corresponding to the measures x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n .

3. Let me now point out some aspects of this proof:

1°. When we try to demonstrate the principle of the arithmetical mean, if we accept it when we have only two measures, we can assume it true without further effort when the number of measures is 2^k ; it is a bit less immediate to assume it true in the remaining cases.

2°. We don't necessarily need to write the function $f\left(\frac{s_3 - x_3}{2}, x_3\right)$ as $\varphi(s_3)$: it could be whatever function of both s_3 and of another symmetric function of the measures x_1, x_2, x_3 .

3°. We can't say with absolute certainty that the operation we have indicated φ does not assume different expressions according to the values assumed by the measures: it is possible that when $x_1 = x_2 = x_3 = x$, φ degenerates to a division by 3, in the same way as s_3 degenerates to a multiplication by 3, while in fact being a completely different operation in the general case.

4. Let me now remind you of another proof which was developed by our distinguished Schiaparelli in 1868, then further refined and published in *Astronomische Nachrichten*, No 2068, year 1875. This proof leans on three postulates.

1°. The most probable value does not depend on the unit of measure, therefore if we indicate its value with the notation

$$U = \varphi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$$

it follows that U is a linear homogenous function⁴ of x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n and, because of a well-known property of such functions⁵, we have

$$U = \frac{\partial U}{\partial x_1} x_1 + \frac{\partial U}{\partial x_2} x_2 + \dots + \frac{\partial U}{\partial x_n} x_n$$

2°. It does not depend on the origin from which we are starting measuring either, hence if we add to each of the measures the same parameter h , U increases by the same value. Thus, if we approximate U with its Taylor polynomial⁶, we conclude that

⁴ We say that $U = U(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ is an homogenous function with respect to its variables, with a degree α , if we have $U(mx_1, mx_2, \dots, mx_n) = m^\alpha U(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$. In particular, if $\alpha = 1$ we say that U is a linear homogenous function.

⁵ Schiaparelli made use of the well-known theorem by Euler which states that if U is a function of x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n with a degree of homogeneity α then we have $\alpha U = \frac{\partial U}{\partial x_1} x_1 + \frac{\partial U}{\partial x_2} x_2 + \dots + \frac{\partial U}{\partial x_n} x_n$.

⁶ The expansion of U with the Taylor series of the first order is $U(x_1 + h, x_2 + h, \dots, x_n + h) = U(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) + \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{\partial U(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)}{\partial x_k} h$. By comparison of this expression with $U(x_1 + h, x_2 + h, \dots, x_n + h) = U(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) + h$, we get the equation reported by Schiaparelli in his second postulate.

$$\frac{\partial U}{\partial x_1} + \frac{\partial U}{\partial x_2} + \dots + \frac{\partial U}{\partial x_n} = 1$$

3°. Assuming that each measure has the same weight, their influence on U has to be the same; which means that the partial derivatives of U with respect to the variables x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n are equal one to the other, in other words:

$$\frac{\partial U}{\partial x_1} = \frac{\partial U}{\partial x_2} = \dots = \frac{\partial U}{\partial x_n}$$

Then it is easy to recognize that

$$U = \frac{x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n}{n}$$

5. The distinguished Stone pointed out some flaws of this proof in *Astronomische Nachrichten*, No. 2092. In particular, he observed that the first two postulates are neither necessary nor evident enough: φ can contain concrete coefficients⁷ and it can be symmetric with respect to the unit of measure, rather than to the measurements⁸; he stated also that the third postulate is evident and that he obtained the thesis from that postulate only with a proof that was published in the issue of the year 1873 of *Monthly Notices*, vol. 33, No 9.

6. In his reply to these observations, in *Astronomische Nachrichten*, No. 2097, the distinguished Schiaparelli claimed for himself the authorship of the third postulate, praised the proof by Stone, apologized for not knowing that demonstration when he developed his own, and asked the readers who were interested in analysing this question more in depth, to judge by themselves for what concerns the plausibility of the first two postulates; he also added that he assumed that both the measures and the most probable value are expressed by numbers of the same type⁹.

7. Yet, it is worth going through the proof by the distinguished Stone with great care and attention¹⁰. Even though this proof emerges from the others, yet it seems to me to be flawed by some imperfections. In what follows you find the whole demonstration by Stone. Let x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n be n measures of the same quantity, all equally probable and taken with the same care. We assume as an axiom that each measure contributes in the same way to the most

⁷ A concrete number is any number accompanied by its unit of measure (for instance: two metres); an absolute number is a number with no unit of measure.

⁸ These are the exact words by Stone Angelitti is referring to: “The assumptions I and II of professor Schiaparelli’s paper are no doubt satisfied by the most probable value ... but their introduction is unnecessary, and their axiomatic character is doubtful; for a function may involve concrete as well as abstract coefficients, and although if we change the unit adopted for the measures a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n we must necessarily change the value of the function in the same proportion, it does not follow that the function must be homogeneous with respect to the variables a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n , although it must be homogenous with respect to the unit adopted”.

⁹ In Schiaparelli’s own words: “Quant au caractère axiomatique de mes suppositions I et II, j’en laisserai le jugement aux personnes qui voudront bien examiner la question avec quelque soin. Peut-être il sera bon d’avertir, que je suppose mes quantités $a_1, a_2, a_3 \dots$ exprimées en nombres, et que j’entends par $F(a_1, a_2, \dots)$ le résultat d’un certain système d’opérations exécuté sur ces nombres, résultat qui doit être interprété comme un nombre de la même espèce que $a_1, a_2, a_3 \dots$ ”.

¹⁰ The original in Latin here says: “At opere pretium erit summa cura studioque considerare...” I think that *opere* (ablative singular of the neuter noun *opus*, *operis* = work, achievement) might here be a mistyping for *operae* (genitive singular of the feminine noun *opera*, *operae* = work, care). As a confirmation of this hypothesis, in *Ab Urbe condita*, vol. III, par. 26, Titus Livius writes: “Operae pretium est audire...”

probable value. Which means that an existing error or arbitrary change in one of the measures, let's say in x_1 , will produce in the most probable value the same change that would be produced by an error or change of the same magnitude in x_2 , or in x_3 , ..., or in x_n .

If we indicate $U = \varphi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ the most probable value, since we assume that the same variation in each of the measures x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n produces the same effect on U , then the following relationships among the derivatives must be true:

$$\frac{\partial U}{\partial x_1} = \frac{\partial U}{\partial x_2} = \dots = \frac{\partial U}{\partial x_n}$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial x_1^2} = \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial x_2^2} = \dots = \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial x_n^2}$$

Therefore

$$\frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} = \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial x_1^2} = \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial x_2^2} = \text{etc.}$$

Hence, generally

$$\frac{\partial^{r+s} U}{\partial x_1^r \partial x_2^s} = \frac{\partial^{r+s} U}{\partial x_1^{r+s}} = \frac{\partial^{r+s} U}{\partial x_2^{r+s}} = \text{etc.}$$

Now, let $x_1 = a_1 + h_1, x_2 = a_2 + h_2, \dots, x_n = a_n + h_n$. Then we have¹¹

$$U(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \varphi(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) + \left(h_1 \frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} + h_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial x_2} + \dots + h_n \frac{\partial}{\partial x_n} \right) U(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) +$$

$$+ \frac{1}{2!} \left(h_1 \frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} + h_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial x_2} + \dots + h_n \frac{\partial}{\partial x_n} \right)^2 U(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) + \dots +$$

$$+ \frac{1}{r!} \left(h_1 \frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} + h_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial x_2} + \dots + h_n \frac{\partial}{\partial x_n} \right)^r U(a_1 + \theta h_1, a_2 + \theta h_2, \dots, a_n + \theta h_n)$$

By substituting the conditions on the derivatives, we have

$$U(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \varphi(A) + (h_1 + h_2 + \dots + h_n) \frac{\partial U(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n)}{\partial x_1} +$$

$$+ \frac{1}{2!} (h_1 + h_2 + \dots + h_n) \frac{\partial^2 U(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n)}{\partial x_1^2} + \dots +$$

$$+ \frac{1}{r!} (h_1 + h_2 + \dots + h_n)^r \frac{\partial^r U(a_1 + \theta h_1, a_2 + \theta h_2, \dots, a_n + \theta h_n)}{\partial x_1^r}$$

¹¹ This is the Taylor polynomial of U of degree $r - 1$, centred in (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) with Lagrange remainder. It is implicitly assumed that $\theta \in]0,1[$.

This expression must be true for any value of a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n , so, in particular, let us consider the case in which

$$a_1 = a_2 = \dots a_n = s = \frac{x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n}{n}$$

then we have¹²

$$h_1 + h_2 + \dots + h_n = 0$$

Therefore

$$U(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \varphi(s, s, \dots, s) = \Psi(s)$$

which means that U is a function of the arithmetical mean.

If we now consider the case in which we only have two measures, then it is obvious that the most probable value is the arithmetical mean itself since no reason can be assigned why we should adopt a value nearer to one than to the other measure.

Let us now assume that the most probable value is the arithmetical mean when we have n measures, in other words:

$$\Psi\left(\frac{x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n}{n}\right) = \frac{x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n}{n}$$

or $\Psi(s) = s$.

Then, in the case of $n + 1$ measures we have

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi\left(\frac{x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n + x_{n+1}}{n + 1}\right) &= \Psi\left(\frac{ns + x_{n+1}}{n + 1}\right) = \\ &= \Psi\left(s + \frac{x_{n+1} - s}{n + 1}\right) = \\ &= \Psi(s) + \frac{x_{n+1} - s}{n + 1} \Psi'(s) + \frac{1}{2!} \left(\frac{x_{n+1} - s}{n + 1}\right)^2 \Psi''(s) + \dots \end{aligned}$$

But $\Psi(s) = s$ by assumption, then $\Psi'(s) = 1$; moreover $\Psi^{(k)}(s) = 0$ for $k = 2, 3, 4, \dots$ Then:

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi\left(\frac{x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n + x_{n+1}}{n + 1}\right) &= s + \frac{x_{n+1} - s}{n + 1} = \frac{ns + x_{n+1}}{n + 1} = \\ &= \frac{x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n + x_{n+1}}{n + 1} \end{aligned}$$

Then it is true that also for $n + 1$ the most probable value is the arithmetical mean. So, we can conclude that the most probable value is always the arithmetical mean.

8. Let me now point out some observations regarding this proof.

¹² In fact, since $h_i = x_i - a_i$, then we have $h_i = x_i - \frac{x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n}{n} \Rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^n h_i = (\sum_{i=1}^n x_i) - n \frac{x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n}{n} = 0$.

1°. First, the distinguished Stone seems to set an infinite number of conditions, since his proof leans on the identity between the partial derivatives not only of the first order but also of any other higher order. This is an unnecessary complication that can be easily avoided, as I am going to show in what follows.

2°. Assuming that the principle of the arithmetical mean is true in the case of only two measures is not so much less than assuming it true for whatever number of measures.

3°. Moreover, the following part of the proof is pointless: the one in which the author tries to demonstrate that if $\Psi(s) = s$ when we have n measures, then the same happens when the measures are $n + 1$. Actually, the meaning of the operation represented in the first member by Ψ is completely unknown and since the notation Ψ in the second member has the same meaning, it is not possible to claim that $\Psi(s) = s$. It would have been necessary to use a different symbol for the operation and the arithmetical mean for each value of the number of measures: in the case of n measures x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n by indicating with s_n the arithmetical mean and with $\Psi_n(s_n)$ the most probable value, we assume that $\Psi_n(s_n) = s_n$; that said, in the case of $n + 1$ measures $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, x_{n+1}$ we then indicate s_{n+1} the arithmetical mean and $\Psi_{n+1}(s_{n+1})$ the relative most probable value. Now we must prove that $\Psi_{n+1}(s_{n+1}) = s_{n+1}$. The expansion with Taylor series gives:

$$\Psi_{n+1}(s_{n+1}) = \Psi_{n+1}(s_n) + \frac{x_{n+1} - s_n}{n + 1} \Psi'_{n+1}(s_n) + \frac{1}{2!} \left(\frac{x_{n+1} - s_n}{n + 1} \right)^2 \Psi''_{n+1}(s_n) + \dots$$

But we don't know what $\Psi_{n+1}(s_{n+1})$ and $\Psi_{n+1}(s_n)$ are, so it is not possible to proceed with our proof. The notation used by Stone has introduced an error that has been concealed by the fact that it leads to the correct result purely by chance. In fact, if Stone had indicated the most probable value as a function $\chi(S)$, with $S = x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n$ and $\chi(S) = S/n$, then he would have had to prove that

$$\chi(S + x_{n+1}) = \frac{x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n + x_{n+1}}{n + 1}$$

But if we now use the method he used in his proof with this new notation, we have

$$\chi(S + x_{n+1}) = \chi(S) + x_{n+1} \chi'(S) + \frac{1}{2!} x_{n+1}^2 \chi''(S) + \dots$$

Since $\chi'(S) = 1/n$ and $\chi''(S) = 0$, then it is obvious that Stone's proof is deceiving. Besides, it is well known that the expansion by Taylor series is not suitable for investigating an unknown function if we do not provide further information about the function itself.

Therefore, the proof by the distinguished Stone leans on two postulates rather than on only one, and what is even worse, it remains unsure.

9. It seems to me that the distinguished Stone does not make himself clear when he criticizes the proof by our Schiaparelli, either. In particular, for what concerns the first postulate, the evidence of which Stone tries to weaken, it is hard to understand in which way the concrete coefficients are introduced, since when we try to calculate the most probable value, we do not consider the unit of measure and it is not relevant for us if the numbers we are dealing with are radians of an arc or millimetres of a line. Moreover, we can enunciate this same postulate in a completely abstract version, saying that if we multiply each measure by a certain number, then the most probable value must be multiplied by the same number too. The evidence of this proposition arises from the methods themselves that we use in our

observations: in fact, we rarely take the measures directly, most of the time we measure something proportional to them (like for instance when we measure an angle by measuring an arc of the circumference that has that angle in its centre, or when we measure a small part of a circumference magnified by an instrument) and we do not doubt that those measures that we aim at obtaining, increase or decrease according to the same proportion.

The distinguished Stone put into question the second postulate too, even though he objected nothing about it. The evidence of the second postulate emerges, as well, from the methods we use whether in experimental observations or in calculations. In fact, when we know a distance between two origins, whether by measurement or by some theoretic speculation, we often substitute one origin to the other in our calculations; we do that when we attribute to a measure its closest value obtained by our instruments. In our calculations, we often attribute approximate values to our unknowns for which we set the small corrections to add. In any case, we retain that the most probable value increases or decreases by the same quantity the measures themselves do.

The third postulate is not so obvious, in truth, as Stone seems to believe. In fact, it not only can't be considered based on common knowledge, but it can't even be understood by a person who does not have expertise in calculus and it requires an explanation: indeed the distinguished Schiaparelli superbly illustrated it in two ways. In fact, the third postulate is nothing else than an analytic definition of the hypothesis that we express, using everyday language, assuming that the measures are all analogously reliable and that they have the same weight and contribute equally at determining the most probable value. To enunciate this condition analytically, firstly we accept that the most probable value is a function $U = \varphi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ of the measures x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n , limited and continue in the whole domain in which the measures themselves span, that admits at least the partial derivatives of the first order,

$$\frac{\partial U}{\partial x_1} = \varphi'_{x_1}(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$$

$$\frac{\partial U}{\partial x_2} = \varphi'_{x_2}(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$$

...

$$\frac{\partial U}{\partial x_n} = \varphi'_{x_n}(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$$

they too limited and continue in the same domain; that said, it is clear that the measures have the same weight when an infinite small variation δx , whatever is the measure it is applied to, produces the same infinite small variation δU in the function U , so that the incremental ratio $\delta U / \delta x$ and its limit do not depend on the variable the variation δx was assigned to: therefore, all the partial derivatives of the first order are equal to the same function that we shall indicate $\varphi'(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$. For these reasons, the proof by the distinguished Schiaparelli, based on these three postulates, remains a sound one, in my opinion.

Nevertheless, since the first postulate has been put into question once and this rust has perhaps corrupted some souls¹³, I have tried to develop a new proof which doesn't rely on that postulate and only leans on the other two, instead.

¹³ In the original: "haec aerugo quosdam forsitan animos imbuerit". I found a somehow similar sentence in Horace's *Ars Poetica* (v. 330-331), that might have represented perhaps the inspiration for it: "An haec animos aerugo et cura peculi / cum semel imbuerit..."

Let me now submit my own proof, which is on the same line of the previous ones, to the judgement of the benevolent readers.

10. Given the measures x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n with the same weight, let's indicate $U = \varphi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ the most probable value relative to them. Assuming that all the partial derivatives¹⁴ of U itself are equal to the same function $\varphi'(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$, first of all, I demonstrate that U is a function of the arithmetical mean of the aforementioned measures; to do that, I will follow Stone's footsteps; but I will stop at the first term of the expansion with the Taylor series, using the remainder¹⁵ instead of the second term. Therefore, if a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n are values near to x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n , we can write¹⁶

$$U = \varphi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \varphi(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) + \varphi'(\xi_1, \xi_2, \dots, \xi_n) \sum_{k=1}^n (x_k - a_k)$$

where $\xi_k \in]x_k, a_k[$ with $k = 1, 2, \dots, n$. Now, if we put

$$a_1 = a_2 = \dots = a_n = M = \frac{x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n}{n}$$

we have $\sum_{k=1}^n (x_k - a_k) = 0$ and since $\varphi'(\xi_1, \xi_2, \dots, \xi_n)$ is limited, then

$$U = \varphi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \varphi(M, M, \dots, M) = \psi(M) = \psi\left(\frac{x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n}{n}\right)$$

We could attain the same conclusion more elegantly.

In fact, since the rows of the Jacobian matrix of the two functions U and M

$$\left\| \begin{array}{cccc} \frac{\partial U}{\partial x_1} & \frac{\partial U}{\partial x_2} & \dots & \frac{\partial U}{\partial x_n} \\ \frac{\partial M}{\partial x_1} & \frac{\partial M}{\partial x_2} & \dots & \frac{\partial M}{\partial x_n} \end{array} \right\|$$

are proportional¹⁷, then it follows that U is a function of M , namely $U = \psi(M)$ ¹⁸. Now, to investigate the structure of the function ψ , I add to all the measures the same quantity h so that the expansion by the Taylor series gives

$$\psi\left(\frac{(x_1 + h) + (x_2 + h) + \dots + (x_n + h)}{n}\right) = \psi(M + h) =$$

¹⁴ Of the first order.

¹⁵ This is the Lagrange remainder.

¹⁶ In the following equation I have used the notation $\sum_{k=1}^n (x_k - a_k)$ instead of the one used by Angelitti, $[(x - a)]$, which is uncommon nowadays. I will use the operator Σ for the sum in what follows too, everywhere it is required, instead of the brackets.

¹⁷ Each element of the first row is equal to φ' , while each element of the second row is equal to $\frac{1}{n}$, so they indeed are proportional.

¹⁸ In fact, since $U = \psi(M) \Leftrightarrow \frac{\partial U}{\partial x_k} = \psi'(M) \frac{\partial M}{\partial x_k}$, it follows that $\psi'(M)$ is the proportion between the two rows of the Jacobian matrix.

$$= \psi(M) + h\psi'(M) + \frac{h^2}{2!}\psi''(M) + \dots + \frac{h^r}{r!}\psi^{(r)}(M + \theta h)$$

On the other hand, the second postulate by the distinguished Schiaparelli gives

$$\psi\left(\frac{(x_1 + h) + (x_2 + h) + \dots + (x_n + h)}{n}\right) = \psi(M) + h$$

So, by comparison, we conclude that

$$\psi'(M) = 1$$

By integration of this equation, we immediately have

$$\psi(M) = M + C$$

where C represents the arbitrary constant of integration. The particular case in which it is $x_1 = x_2 = \dots = x_n = x$, that appeared to be not perfectly suitable to investigate the form of the function, in the proof by the distinguished Encke, in the present situation perfectly serves the scope of determining the constant number C . Since in this case, we have $M = x$ and we also know that it must be $\psi(M) = x^{19}$, then we can conclude that $C = 0$. Therefore, we have

$$U = \psi(M) = M$$

and the most probable value is the arithmetical mean itself.

11. In a quite analogous way, it is possible to determine the most probable value associated to a set of measures, each with a different weight, if we properly define the analytical conditions that the value itself must verify. In this case, each measure must contribute to that value accordingly to its weight, so to speak. To translate this condition analytically, let's consider the measures x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n with weights p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n , respectively: then we understand that the most probable value is a function $U = \varphi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ such that, if we assign to each measure the same infinitely small variation δx , then U changes accordingly by values proportional to the weights p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n ; so that the expressions $\frac{1}{p_1} \cdot \frac{\partial U}{\partial x_1}, \frac{1}{p_2} \cdot \frac{\partial U}{\partial x_2}, \dots, \frac{1}{p_n} \cdot \frac{\partial U}{\partial x_n}$ are all equal to the same function $\varphi'(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$. Moreover, assuming true also in this case the second postulate proposed by the distinguished Schiaparelli, we assume that if all the measures are increased by the same value h , then the most probable value must increase by the same value too. All that said, we have

$$U = \varphi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \varphi(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) + \varphi'(\xi_1, \xi_2, \dots, \xi_n) \sum_{k=1}^n p_k(x_k - a_k)$$

Now, if we put

¹⁹ In this case all the measures are equal to x , then we can confidently say that x is the most probable value.

$$a_1 = a_2 = \dots = a_n = P = \frac{x_1 p_1 + x_2 p_2 + \dots + x_n p_n}{p_1 + p_2 + \dots + p_n}$$

we get $\sum_{k=1}^n p_k (x_k - a_k) = 0$ and thus it follows that

$$U = \varphi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \varphi(P, P, \dots, P) = \psi(P) = \psi\left(\frac{x_1 p_1 + x_2 p_2 + \dots + x_n p_n}{p_1 + p_2 + \dots + p_n}\right)$$

In this case also, the Jacobian matrix

$$\left\| \begin{array}{cccc} \frac{\partial U}{\partial x_1} & \frac{\partial U}{\partial x_2} & \dots & \frac{\partial U}{\partial x_n} \\ \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_1} & \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_2} & \dots & \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_n} \end{array} \right\|$$

has two proportional rows²⁰ which means that $U = \psi(P)$ ²¹.

To determine the structure of the function ψ , let us add to each measure the same quantity h : the expansion by the Taylor series gives

$$\begin{aligned} \psi\left(\frac{p_1(x_1 + h) + p_2(x_2 + h) + \dots + p_n(x_n + h)}{p_1 + p_2 + \dots + p_n}\right) &= \psi(P + h) = \\ &= \psi(P) + h\psi'(P) + \frac{h^2}{2!}\psi''(P) + \dots + \frac{h^r}{r!}\psi^{(r)}(P + \theta h) \end{aligned}$$

while according to the second postulate

$$\psi\left(\frac{p_1(x_1 + h) + p_2(x_2 + h) + \dots + p_n(x_n + h)}{p_1 + p_2 + \dots + p_n}\right) = \psi(P) + h$$

Hence, we conclude that

$$\psi'(P) = 1$$

By integration of this equation we get

$$U = \psi(P) = P + C$$

In order to calculate the constant of integration, let us consider the case $x_1 = x_2 = \dots = x_n = x$: since in this case we have $P = x$ and, on the other hand, we are confident in saying that $\psi(P) = x$, then we conclude that $C = 0$. Thus, we have

$$U = P = \frac{x_1 p_1 + x_2 p_2 + \dots + x_n p_n}{p_1 + p_2 + \dots + p_n}$$

²⁰ The first row is $[p_1 \varphi' \quad p_2 \varphi' \quad \dots \quad p_n \varphi']$ while the second one is $\left[\frac{p_1}{\sum_1^n p_k} \quad \frac{p_2}{\sum_1^n p_k} \quad \dots \quad \frac{p_n}{\sum_1^n p_k}\right]$, so we can obtain the second row by multiplying the first one by $\frac{\varphi'}{\sum_1^n p_k}$.

²¹ As in footnote 18.

The name of P is weighted mean.

In the case in which the weights p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n are integer numbers – a case we can always turn into by not considering the weights given, but instead a set of numbers proportional to them – then this analysis shows that the measures x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n can be considered the arithmetical means of p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n measures with a unitary weight each²².

12. In the previous discussion, we have supposed that the most probable value deduced from several measures is a function of the measures themselves. This is the nature of the most probable value that differentiates it from a real value. In fact, the real value is meant, from a mathematical point of view, as a constant that is not influenced by our measures. Hence, what happens is that the real value is never reached by our measures and it continuously eludes our best efforts, even when we assume that the measures themselves are only subjected to random errors.

In the previous passages, we have seen that the most probable value is expressed rigorously by the arithmetical mean. It is not completely clear to me the reason why Gauss stated that the arithmetical mean could only be an approximation of the most probable value, rather than its rigorous value: perhaps he meant the most probable value as defined by an infinite number of measures, while we have dealt with only a finite number of them.

Palermo, March 24th, 1910

Filippo Angelitti

²² In fact, let's say that x_1 is the arithmetical mean of the p_1 measures $x_{1,1}, x_{1,2}, \dots, x_{1,p_1}$, then we have $x_1 = \frac{x_{1,1} + x_{1,2} + \dots + x_{1,p_1}}{p_1}$. The same applies to the other measures and we can write:

$$P = \frac{x_1 p_1 + x_2 p_2 + \dots + x_n p_n}{p_1 + p_2 + \dots + p_n} =$$

$$= \frac{\frac{x_{1,1} + x_{1,2} + \dots + x_{1,p_1}}{p_1} p_1 + \frac{x_{2,1} + x_{2,2} + \dots + x_{2,p_2}}{p_2} p_2 + \dots + \frac{x_{n,1} + x_{n,2} + \dots + x_{n,p_n}}{p_n} p_n}{p_1 + p_2 + \dots + p_n} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^n \sum_{h=1}^{p_h} x_{kh}}{\sum_{h=1}^n p_h}$$

and the weighted mean becomes an arithmetical mean of $\sum_{h=1}^n p_h$ measures of the same weight.

Again on the Principle of Arithmetical Mean

1. In the article I published in the issue of July 1910 of *Astronomische Nachrichten*, No. 4424 (vol. 185, from page 113) about the principle of arithmetical mean, I proposed a new proof for that principle, in paragraphs 10 and 11, both in case of measures with the same weight and in case of measures with a different weight. Let me now add some observations on how these proofs can be further refined and on how more simple proofs can be developed.

2. The proof that I developed for the case of measures with the same weight leans on three postulates and it is made up of three parts.

In the first part, by assuming that the most probable value U is a function $\varphi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ of the measures x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n with the derivatives of the first order all equal to the same function $\varphi'(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$, I showed that U is a function $\psi(M)$ of the arithmetical mean M of the measures themselves; and I proved it by two different methods, both by expansion with Taylor series and by using a Jacobian matrix

In the second section of my proof, by assuming that the most probable value must increase by a quantity h when all the measures increase by the same quantity h , I showed that $\psi'(M) = 1$. To prove this, I made use of the expansion by Taylor series without it being truly necessary. We recognize in fact that after the increase in the measures, the most probable function becomes

$$\psi(M + h) = \psi(M) + h$$

therefore

$$\frac{\psi(M + h) - \psi(M)}{h} = 1$$

and by the definition of derivative of a function, it follows

$$\psi'(M) = 1$$

If we had concluded in the previous part of this proof that the most probable value was a function $\chi(S)$ of the sum S of all the measures, then by adding the same value to all the measures, we would have had

$$\chi(S + nh) = \chi(S) + h$$

which gives

$$\frac{\chi(S + nh) - \chi(S)}{nh} = \frac{1}{n}$$

Therefore

$$\chi'(S) = \frac{1}{n}$$

and the conclusion would have been the same.

In the last section of the proof, I found by integration that $U = M + C$ and I proved that $C = 0$ by considering the particular case in which $x_1 = x_2 = \dots = x_n = x$ and $U = x$.

3. But the assumption of the second postulate is unnecessary, after all. For, if in the equation where we expanded the function by the Taylor series of the second order

$$U = \varphi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \varphi(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) + \varphi'(\xi_1, \xi_2, \dots, \xi_n) \sum_{k=1}^n (x_k - a_k)$$

we set the values a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n so that $\sum_{k=1}^n x_k = \sum_{k=1}^n a_k$, then we would have

$$U = \varphi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \varphi(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n)$$

Therefore, the function which provides the most probable value maintains the same form and the same value when we replace the measures with other measures with the same sum. Then by substituting the measures with their arithmetical mean,²³ we have

$$U = \varphi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \varphi(M, M, \dots, M)$$

But when all the measures have the same value, then we can assume that the most probable value is equal to it too, then we have

$$U = M$$

4. If we want to lean on the properties of Jacobian matrices instead, to craft the proof, let us consider the function

$$S = x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n$$

Then²⁴ we have

$$\begin{vmatrix} \frac{\partial U}{\partial x_1} & \frac{\partial U}{\partial x_2} & \dots & \frac{\partial U}{\partial x_n} \\ \frac{\partial S}{\partial x_1} & \frac{\partial S}{\partial x_2} & \dots & \frac{\partial S}{\partial x_n} \end{vmatrix} = 0$$

Therefore, U is a function $\chi(S)$ of the sum S . Now it is clear that the value of the function $\chi(S)$, which is the value of U , does not change if we substitute the measures with another set of measures with the same sum. We can, for instance, consider a set of measures all equal to the arithmetical mean of x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n and in this case, we have $U = M$.

5. The last passages of these two proofs are both unaffected by the flaw that I attributed to the demonstration by Encke, in my previous paper. He, in fact, did not manage to prove with sufficient rigour that the most probable value is a function only of the sum of the measures,

²³ The arithmetical mean of x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n – let us say M – is in fact such that $x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n = nM$.

²⁴ Here Angelitti is saying that the rows of the Jacobian are proportional: for the first one is made up by elements all equals to $\frac{\partial U}{\partial x_1}$, while the second one has all its elements given by 1.

and he assumed that the nature of the function remains the same for each possible set of measures.

6. It is possible to develop a proof based on the same postulates the previous one leans on, without the use of any notion of calculus. In fact, when we add to one of the measures, whatever it is, an increment h , then it follows by the first and second postulate²⁵ that the most probable value increases by a value h/n ; so that the ratio between the increase in the most probable value and the increase in one of the measures is always $1/n$, whichever the measure is. This means that

$$U = \varphi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \varphi(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) + \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n (x_k - a_k)$$

Now, by using the same method presented in the paragraphs above, we can conclude that

$$U = \varphi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \varphi(M, M, \dots, M) = M$$

7. The distinguished Dr R. Suppanschitsch, while reading *Zur Axiomatik der Methode der kleinsten Quadrate* during the conference of the Akademie der Wissenschaften of Wien, held in January 1931, objected about my previous paper that I derived the principle of the arithmetical mean with calculations, from postulates it almost directly is deduced from; if he meant with these words that he would have preferred a greater simplicity in this proof, he certainly was right, and he will perhaps welcome this last demonstration with a more positive judgment. Moreover, I just followed the footsteps of the previous authors who made use of calculus, even if it is a more complex tool.

8. In the last passage of the proofs reported previously, I have imitated the way of thinking that the distinguished Pizzetti followed in his classic work entitled *I fondamenti matematici per la critica dei risultati sperimentali* (Genoa, 1891, pp. 92-93), where, in referring and carefully weighting the disquisitions by other scientists about the principle of the arithmetical mean, he himself proposed, as a personal conclusion²⁶, a proof built on two

²⁵ In this paper the first postulate is the one reminded at the beginning of paragraph 2, namely the assumption that the partial derivatives are all equal one to the other. The second postulate is the one reminded some lines below: the one that states that if we increase all the measures by the same value h , then U increases by the same value. This enumeration is different from the one used in the previous paper and this might lead to some confusion.

²⁶ This is an almost literal translation into English of the proof by Pizzetti, cited in this paper: "... we can observe that when the errors of measure are small enough that their powers above the first order and their products are negligible, then the principle of arithmetical mean derives directly from the two following postulates:

- a) the most convenient value is a symmetric function of the measures.
- b) when all the measures are equal to the same number, then the most convenient value is that number.

Let us indicate M the arithmetical mean, l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n the measures, and $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_n$ the differences between the measures and M . Then we have:

$$u = f(l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n) = f(M + \lambda_1, M + \lambda_2, \dots, M + \lambda_n)$$

The evolution by the Taylor series, neglecting the terms above the first order, gives

$$u = f(M, M, \dots, M) + \lambda_1 \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial l_1} \right)_M + \lambda_2 \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial l_2} \right)_M + \dots + \lambda_n \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial l_n} \right)_M$$

postulates, assuming first that the most convenient value, using his own expression²⁷, is a symmetric function of the measures, and secondly that, as we also admitted, when all the measures are equal to the same value, then the most convenient value must be equal to it too.

This proof, because of the greatest importance of the first postulate, should have been preferred to all the others, if the distinguished author had not needed to rely on the supposition that the differences between the measures and the arithmetical mean are small quantities of the first order so that products and powers of the second, third, and higher orders can be neglected; this is, in fact, the only possible situation in which we can consider the arithmetical mean in place of the measures it is calculated from when we are dealing with a symmetric function. So it happens that the most convenient value is given only in the proximity of the arithmetical mean and that we take for granted that the squares of the differences between the measures and the arithmetical mean can be neglected, even though they are coefficients of functions of great relevance.

Moreover, from a practical perspective, the differences between the measures and the arithmetical mean can't be defined as small or big, if not in comparison to a known quantity, or to the unity. The determination of such a quantity does not seem to be an easy task. If for instance, we measure the distance between the two components of a double star²⁸, it is not clear whether the differences between the measures and the arithmetical mean are to be referred to the radius of the trigonometric circumference or to the measured value itself. Moreover, from a theoretical standpoint, the proposition according to which the arithmetical mean can be substituted to the variables – different two by two – of a symmetric function without changing its value, encounters an even greater difficulty and it sometimes leads to a contradiction. For instance, the function $\sqrt[n]{\prod_{k=1}^n x_k}$ where the variables x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n are small quantities, part positive, part negative, can assume an imaginary value, while $\sqrt[n]{M^n} = M$ is always a positive number.

9. Similarly, it is possible to further refine the proof I provided in paragraph 11 of my previous paper, for the case of measures with different weights.

First, where it was proved that the most probable value is a function $\psi(P)$ of the weighted mean P , it could have been shown that $\psi'(P) = 1$ without the use of the Taylor series. In fact, added to all the measures the quantity h , since the weighted mean increases by the same quantity, the most probable value becomes $\psi(P + h)$; but according to the second postulate it also becomes $\psi(P) + h$; hence, it follows

Since f is a symmetric function of l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n , it follows that

$$\left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial l_1}\right)_M = \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial l_2}\right)_M = \dots = \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial l_n}\right)_M$$

On the other hand, the sum $\sum_{k=1}^n \lambda_k$ is zero, then

$$u = f(M, M, \dots, M)$$

Hence, postulate b leads to the conclusion $u = M$."

²⁷ The expression used by Pizzetti is "il valore più conveniente" and this is a more appropriate name than the one used by Gauss and by his fellow-mathematicians, since it reflects the fact, as some readers probably well know, that the expectation of a distribution (in other words, its arithmetical mean) is not necessarily its most probable value.

²⁸ I think that Angelitti here refers to the components of proper motion on the celestial sphere. The distance between two stars of a binary system is the magnitude of the vector obtained as the difference between the proper motions of the two stars.

$$\psi(P + h) = \psi(P) + h$$

therefore, by definition of derivative of a function, it follows

$$\psi'(P) = 1$$

10. But the assumption of the second postulate is unnecessary. In fact, the equation

$$U = \varphi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \varphi(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) + \varphi'(\xi_1, \xi_2, \dots, \xi_n) \sum_{k=1}^n p_k(x_k - a_k)$$

which is deduced from the assumption of the first postulate, immediately gives

$$U = \varphi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \varphi(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n)$$

when $\sum_{k=1}^n p_k(x_k - a_k) = 0$ or, equivalently, $\sum_{k=1}^n p_k x_k = \sum_{k=1}^n p_k a_k$. Therefore, it is always possible to substitute the measures with other measures under the condition that the sum of their products by the respective weights stays the same. Which means, in particular, that we can consider the weighted mean, in place of each measure²⁹; and we have

$$U = \varphi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \varphi(P, P, \dots, P) = P$$

11. Moreover, by assuming the same postulates the previous proof was based on, here also we can provide another demonstration that does not lean on any notion of calculus. In fact, assuming both the first and the second postulate, it follows that the increase of the most probable value corresponding to an increase h of the measures x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n , is $\frac{p_1 h}{\sum_{k=1}^n p_k}, \frac{p_2 h}{\sum_{k=1}^n p_k}, \dots, \frac{p_n h}{\sum_{k=1}^n p_k}$, respectively. From this, we deduce that

$$U = \varphi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \varphi(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) + \frac{\sum_{k=1}^n p_k(x_k - a_k)}{\sum_{k=1}^n p_k}$$

thus, we hasten to the conclusion by the same reasoning we used in the previous paragraph.

Palermo, March 25th, 1914

Filippo Angelitti

²⁹ We have $\sum_{k=1}^n p_k P = P \sum_{k=1}^n p_k = \frac{x_1 p_1 + x_2 p_2 + \dots + x_n p_n}{\sum_{k=1}^n p_k} \cdot \sum_{k=1}^n p_k = \sum_{k=1}^n p_k x_k$.

Something More on the Principle of Arithmetical Mean

1. I am compelled to add some further note to the article I recently published in *Astronomische Nachrichten*, No. 4737, about the principle of the arithmetical mean. In fact, after Dr A. Sellerio, once a pupil of mine, showed me a new way with a friendly and thoughtful letter, I have been able to put those same proofs that I brought forward in paragraphs 3 and 10, only based on two postulates, in a form that does not rely on the support of any tool of calculus.

2. Let $\varphi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ be the most probable value rising from the measures with the same weight x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n .

We can enunciate the first postulate with the equation

$$\varphi(x_1 + h, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \varphi(x_1, x_2 + h, \dots, x_n) = \dots = \varphi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n + h)$$

and the other one with the equation

$$\varphi(a, a, \dots, a) = a$$

From the first postulate, we deduce

$$\varphi(x_1 + h_1, x_2 + h_2, \dots, x_n + h_n) = \varphi\left(x_1 + \sum_{k=1}^n h_k, x_2, \dots, x_n\right)$$

If $\sum_{k=1}^n h_k = 0$ or, in other words, $\sum_{k=1}^n (x_k + h_k) = \sum_{k=1}^n x_k$, then

$$\varphi(x_1 + h_1, x_2 + h_2, \dots, x_n + h_n) = \varphi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$$

If, in particular, $nM = \sum_{k=1}^n x_k$, then we have³⁰

$$\varphi(M, M, \dots, M) = \varphi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$$

and by the second postulate

$$M = \varphi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$$

Therefore, the arithmetical mean M is the most probable value.

3. Similarly, let $\varphi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ be the most probable value rising from the measures x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n , with weight p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n , respectively.

Then we can enunciate the first postulate using the equation

$$\varphi\left(x_1 + \frac{h}{p_1}, x_2, \dots, x_n\right) = \varphi\left(x_1, x_2 + \frac{h}{p_2}, \dots, x_n\right) = \dots = \varphi\left(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n + \frac{h}{p_n}\right)$$

³⁰ In this case we assume that $h_k = M - x_k$ and we have $\sum_{k=1}^n h_k = \sum_{k=1}^n (M - x_k) = nM - \sum_{k=1}^n x_k = 0$. Thus, we fall in the situation in which the previous equation holds. In this case we also have: $x_1 + h_1 = x_2 + h_2 = \dots = x_n + h_n = M$.

From this postulate, it follows that³¹

$$\varphi(x_1 + h_1, x_2 + h_2, \dots, x_n + h_n) = \varphi\left(x_1 + \frac{\sum_{k=1}^n p_k h_k}{p_1}, x_2, \dots, x_n\right)$$

If $\sum_{k=1}^n p_k h_k = 0$ or, in other words, $\sum_{k=1}^n (x_k + p_k h_k) = \sum_{k=1}^n x_k$, then

$$\varphi(x_1 + h_1, x_2 + h_2, \dots, x_n + h_n) = \varphi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$$

If, in particular, $P \sum_{k=1}^n p_k = \sum_{k=1}^n p_k x_k$, then we have³²

$$\varphi(P, P, \dots, P) = \varphi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$$

therefore, by the second postulate, we have

$$P = \varphi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$$

Hence we conclude that the weighted mean is the most probable value.

Palermo, June 24th, 1914

Filippo Angelitti

³¹ To fix our ideas, let us consider the case of only three measures. First of all, we can write $\varphi(x_1 + h_1, x_2 + h_2, x_3 + h_3) = \varphi\left(x_1 + \frac{h_1 p_1}{p_1}, x_2 + \frac{h_2 p_2}{p_2}, x_3 + \frac{h_3 p_3}{p_3}\right)$. Then, from the first postulate it follows that $\varphi\left(x_1 + \frac{h_1 p_1}{p_1}, x_2 + \frac{h_2 p_2}{p_2}, x_3 + \frac{h_3 p_3}{p_3}\right) = \varphi\left(x_1 + \frac{h_1 p_1}{p_1} + \frac{h_2 p_2}{p_1}, x_2, x_3 + \frac{h_3 p_3}{p_3}\right)$. Applying it again, we get $\varphi\left(x_1 + \frac{h_1 p_1}{p_1} + \frac{h_2 p_2}{p_1}, x_2, x_3 + \frac{h_3 p_3}{p_3}\right) = \varphi\left(x_1 + \frac{h_1 p_1}{p_1} + \frac{h_2 p_2}{p_1} + \frac{h_3 p_3}{p_1}, x_2, x_3\right)$. So, in conclusion: $\varphi(x_1 + h_1, x_2 + h_2, x_3 + h_3) = \varphi\left(x_1 + \frac{h_1 p_1 + h_2 p_2 + h_3 p_3}{p_1}, x_2, x_3\right)$.

³² In this case we assume that $h_k = P - x_k$ and we have $\sum_{k=1}^n p_k h_k = \sum_{k=1}^n (p_k P - p_k x_k) = P \sum_{k=1}^n p_k - \sum_{k=1}^n p_k x_k = 0$. Thus, we fall in the situation in which the previous equation holds. In this case we also have: $x_1 + h_1 = x_2 + h_2 = \dots = x_n + h_n = P$.